

FedRA: A Fully Decentralized Federated Learning Framework for Robust Intelligence Sharing across O-RAN dApps

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Abstract—In this paper, we propose a resilient and fully decentralized federated learning framework specifically adapted for Open Radio Access Networks (O-RAN) named FedRA that enables collaborative intelligence between dApps. At first, we present how FedRA can be deployed in the O-RAN architecture by using already existing interfaces between the well-defined RAN components and how real-time ML applications (dApps) can interact to share their distilled intelligence. Furthermore, the software components of FedRA framework are briefly described, along with the step-by-step deployment workflow, outlining practical guidelines for its implementation. Finally, the FedRA framework is validated in a simulated environment by using both real and simulated datasets that report the time series of the throughput provided by multiple radio units. Two different Machine Learning models that are hosted in FedRA nodes are used, aiming to either detect anomalies in the upcoming network traffic or forecast the data-rate values. In both cases, the resulting accuracy confirms the validity of the FedRA framework in the training process of the cell-specific ML models, as well as the decentralized collaborative intelligence sharing among them. FedRA is also compared to typical client/server approach in terms of achieved model accuracy and network communication cost.

Index Terms—Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN), Deep Learning (DL), dApps, Federated Learning (FL), Anomaly Detection, Supervised Learning, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC)

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Intelligent Open Radio Access Networks

OPEN Radio Access Network (O-RAN) is an emerging concept that enables mobile operators to design and deploy open hardware with flexible radio control in both centralized and distributed architectures across the Radio Access Network (RAN) [1]. The O-RAN Alliance is already involved in beyond 5G network architectures, which are based on the principles of openness and interoperability, successfully

Manuscript received Month Day, Year; revised Month Day, Year and Month Day, Year; accepted Month Day, Year. Date of publication Month Day, Year; date of current version Month Day, Year. This work was partially supported by the "UNified archITecture for Open RAN-enabled Distributed, Scalable and SustainabilitY-enhanced 6G Networks (UNITY-6G)" Project, funded by EU HORIZON-JU-SNS-2024 program, under grant agreement No 101192650. The Associate Editor for this article was Name Surname. (Corresponding author: Sotirios Spantideas.)

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Digital Object Identifier XX.YYYY/TITS.ZZZZ.LLLLLL

incorporating Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML) algorithms that provide intelligent functionalities to the network, ranging from management capabilities to radio resource allocation [2]. In this context, O-RAN aims to make the RAN components more open and programmable, as well as more intelligent and autonomous [1], [3]. For these purposes, enablers such as cloud native functions, data science tools and AI/ML functions to automate and improve RAN performance are utilized in various applications [4], [5]. The key idea is to disaggregate the RAN blocks, using open software components and interfaces, which allow operators to integrate RAN functions from different vendors [6]. This is the first step before AI/ML models can assist in complex RAN operations, such as placing network function chains in the edge/cloud continuum and use agent-based distributed techniques to solve problems that require high security and trust.

To this end, O-RAN Alliance defines open interfaces between the components of the RAN architecture and separates the RAN functions of the layers above the physical into the Central Unit (CU) and Distributed Unit (DU) entities, reducing the hardware needed at the cell site. Furthermore, O-RAN specifications define three AI/ML workflows and requirements for the lifecycle and management of intelligent algorithms; one of them involves the training and inference of AI/ML models either in the CU or in the DU [2]. This AI/ML workflow has recently attracted considerable interest, since huge amounts of data is created at the network edge. Therefore, there has been an increasingly pressing requirement to process data that originate from the Radio Units (RUs), used to provide the first-tier network access to the User Equipment (UEs), and the DUs directly at the edge for purposes of lowering the network delay, easing the backhaul network traffic and providing reliable service [7], [8]. Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) solutions also provide the required computational capacity, enabling the flexible deployment of AI/ML-assisted applications and services [6]. The intelligent distributed applications deployed in DU/CU are named dApps, extending the functionality of xApps and rApps to support AI/ML services at real time timescales [9].

B. Challenges and Contributions

Recent studies have illustrated the significance of executing AI/ML algorithms at the network edge based on key performance metrics from the physical layer, including Signal to Interference plus Noise Ratio (SINR), latency and allocated

finalized, the ML inference is usually conducted in near-RT RIC, where the ML model is deployed as an xApp, while the model output may be implemented by the RAN entities (the CU, DU or RU can be the actors).

- Control loop 3 works in the non-RT RIC in timescales of more than 500 ms and concerns the functions of management and orchestration, as well as policies to the near-RT RIC. In this case, the ML model is trained based on data obtained through the O1 interface from the RAN and the inference is performed either in the non-RT RIC (the model is deployed as an rApp) or in the near-RT RIC. The actor in this case can be any RAN entity, including the near-RT RIC.

The architectural view of the O-RAN is shown in Fig. 1, along with the interfaces between the RAN components that can be used for data gathering, AI/ML model or parameters exchange and control actions. The deployment of dApps in the DU or CU components can leverage existing O-RAN interfaces, ensuring the compatibility and flexible development. In specific, the dApps that are hosted in the DU can use the O-RAN Open FH to receive data from the RU (southbound) and the E2 interface to receive enrichment information from the near-RT RIC (northbound). Regarding the dApps that reside in the CU, they can extract relevant key performance metrics by the E2 interface (southbound), while also using the E2 interface for enrichment information from the near-RT RIC (northbound) [9]. In both cases, the dApps will use real-time gathered data from the RUs/DUs, for instance UE data rate, I/Q data and beam directionality, along with enrichment information originating from the near-RT RIC to infer the ML model and provide its output in a timely manner [10].

B. Decentralized Federated Learning Framework

In Fig. 1, we illustrate how the ML models that are hosted as dApps in the DUs and CUs can participate in a collaborative learning framework. In specific, we assume that the dApps residing in the DUs utilize RAN data that originate from different RUs and the ML models that are hosted therein target the same optimization or prediction objective. The ML model of each dApp is trained on a different dataset, designated by the observability of the RUs and interconnected UEs. Similar considerations are valid in the case that the dApps are hosted in the CU. Although the CU can be connected to multiple DUs and hence, gathers data from all the RUs/UEs connected to this RAN, it has zero observability to data generated in different RANs.

The proposed architecture abstracts the dApps (either hosted in DUs or CUs) as FedRA nodes in a decentralized FL framework, sharing the intelligence that is distilled from the local datasets. The FedRA framework requires P2P connections among the participating nodes that can be realized by leveraging the O-RAN interfaces. Specifically, the Xn interfaces between RAN nodes in standalone operation can be used to link different CUs. In addition, the O-RAN community is currently developing a D2 interface for inter-O-DU communications, specifically designed for multi-vendor deployments [11].

The architectural view of the FedRA node is demonstrated in Fig. 2. Each dApp hosted in a FedRA node trains its ML

Fig. 2. Architectural view of decentralized FL training across FedRA-enabled Open RAN nodes.

model based on the local dataset for N training epochs. Then, the parameters of the ML model (e.g., the model weights in case of a Deep Neural Network - DNN) are shared between the participating nodes in a P2P fashion. Once each FedRA node has gathered the model parameters from all peers, it performs an FL aggregation process, fusing the intelligence obtained by the different datasets into a single global model. Without loss of generality, we consider the FedAvg strategy as the FL aggregation process in the present work. However, different FL algorithms can be effortlessly introduced, such as FedProx, FedSGD, etc. [12]. The aggregation process completes one round and the learning process is then continued for M FL rounds. Once the training process is completed, the global model is stored in a database, from where it can be retrieved by the dApp online inference module, as depicted in Fig. 2.

It is important to highlight that, although dApps hosted in DU/CU may operate under strict sub-10 ms latency requirements and process large volumes of data (e.g., IQ samples), FedRA decouples the training and inference pipelines. Inference is always prioritized to meet operational deadlines, while training is executed asynchronously using buffered or preprocessed features derived from raw data. Moreover, FedRA can adaptively schedule local training rounds when real-time inference load peaks at certain DUs/CUs. This design ensures that the execution of inference remains uninterrupted and compliant with latency constraints, while decentralized training still progresses in the background.

In comparison to client/server FL architectures, where the near-RT RIC acts as a central aggregator, FedRA nodes act periodically as both clients and servers, performing the ML

model training using the local dataset, while also aggregating the model parameters received from the other participating nodes. To this end, each node in FedRA is fully autonomous, capable of training, aggregating, and contributing to the global model without centralized oversight. Moreover, the decentralized framework provides enhanced data privacy due to the P2P nature of communications, while ensuring resilience. It is worth clarifying that resilience in FedRA does not solely stem from removing the RIC as a central aggregator, but from the ability of the framework to maintain collaborative training even when individual nodes fail or disconnect. In client/server FL, the malfunction of the RIC immediately halts the FL process, whereas in FedRA, the global model continues to evolve with the remaining nodes, enabling continuity of learning. Moreover, decoupling intelligence sharing from the RIC reduces the dependency of FL progress on the availability of a critical O-RAN entity, thus mitigating the risk of cascading failures. Another aspect of resilience offered by FedRA lies in the isolation of D2 interface for model exchange and inter-DU coordination, preventing unnecessary overload of E2 which is used for interconnecting other higher-layer O-RAN nodes.

C. Implementation and Security Considerations

FedRA's architecture includes the following five software components, as depicted in Fig. 2, each playing a crucial role in the decentralized learning process: (i) *P2P Communication Layer* that manages all inter-node communications, from initial peer discovery to ongoing model update exchanges. The communication layer utilizes `libp2p` to ensure secure, efficient, and anonymous P2P interactions, featuring a dynamic peer discovery function, a pub-sub mechanism for efficient broadcast of model updates and network states, a message chunking capability to ensure smooth transmission even in bandwidth-constrained environments and a state synchronization to maintain network-wide consistency; (ii) *Data Management and Preprocessing*, preparing and feeding data to the ML models. This component handles diverse data types and structures, ensuring compatibility across different learning tasks, while implementing advanced preprocessing techniques to optimize learning efficiency; (iii) *Core Operations* module, functioning as the brain of each node by performing critical computations, also managing serialization and de-serialization of model updates. This module is crucial for efficient network transmission and implements the federated aggregation algorithm (e.g., FedAvg); (iv) *Network State Management*, acting as the collective memory of the network by keeping track of the status and contributions of all participating nodes and enabling informed decision-making for adaptive learning strategies; (v) *Orchestration Engine*, coordinating all the above components, managing the lifecycle of the learning process (from initialization to convergence) and implementing high-level learning strategies and protocols.

FedRA's learning process is depicted in Fig. 3 and can be described in the following steps:

- 1) *Network Initialization*: Nodes (DU and CU) join the P2P network using `libp2p`'s peer discovery mechanisms. Each node broadcasts its initial status and capabilities and

Fig. 3. Workflow of the different FedRA processes.

the network collectively establishes initial parameters like learning rate and batch size based on these values.

- 2) *Data Preparation and Local Training*: Nodes preprocess their local datasets, including the testing of the data quality and the scaling functionalities. Initial model architectures are either predefined or negotiated based on the collective dataset characteristics. Each node performs local training, with the flexibility to use custom optimizers and loss functions suited to their data.
- 3) *Model Update Exchange*: Post-training, nodes serialize their model updates, i.e., the neural network weights in case of a DNN model. Updates are strategically disseminated through the network using a combination of direct peer connections and gossip protocols. The P2P network manages the chunking and reassembly of large model updates to ensure reliable transmission.
- 4) *Decentralized Aggregation*: Nodes perform local aggregation of received model updates using the FedAvg algorithm. The aggregation process is weighted based on factors like peer reputation and data quality, as tracked by the Network State Management module. Anomaly detection mechanisms filter out potentially harmful or low-quality updates.
- 5) *Adaptive Learning and Convergence*: The process iterates, with each FL round potentially adapting parameters based on network performance. Convergence is determined through a decentralized consensus mechanism, considering factors like model performance, update magnitude, and network stability. The Network State Management component plays a crucial role in coordinating this decentralized decision-making process.
- 6) *Continuous Evaluation and Refinement*: Throughout the process, nodes continuously evaluate the global model

on their local validation sets. Feedback loops allow for dynamic adjustment of learning rates, batch sizes, and even model architectures. The network can seamlessly handle the joining of new peers or the departure of existing ones, ensuring robustness and scalability.

While FedRA inherently preserves privacy by keeping raw data local, decentralized training also introduces new security challenges such as model-poisoning, Byzantine updates, and malicious peers. To mitigate these risks, the Network State Management module maintains a dynamic reputation score for each peer and filters abnormal updates using gradient-norm and loss-based anomaly checks before local aggregation (Step [10] in Fig. 3). In addition, all peer communications employ mutual authentication and encrypted channels through the `libp2p` framework.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we present the results of the FedRA framework regarding the performance of the ML model training in two different tasks using both simulated and real data: (i) an anomaly detection classification task of the time-varying network traffic based on a synthetic dataset and (ii) a forecasting regression task of the dynamic downlink data-rate based on real data. The above ML tasks have been selected as basic functionalities for network improvement, since the anomaly detection or prediction in the network traffic can affect many network choices for changing resources, such as slice setup, channel use, power control and virtual resource location [13], [14]. To this end, these scenarios consider the AI/ML workflow of O-RAN control loop 1, since the trained cell-specific models can be deployed in the DU, which can be collocated with the RU in the physical infrastructure. In addition, the presented scenarios represent realistic FL training requirements among the fragmented time-series traffic, since it can be considered that the RUs are operated by individual network operators. The ML code runs on a normal PC with the following characteristics: CPU i7-8700, 3.2 GHz, RAM 8 GB with no GPU usage, whereas we deploy each FedRA node that hosts the dApps as separate virtual machines (VMs).

A. Datasets Description

The anomaly detection ML task is in particular a classification task (the ML models outputs 1 if an anomaly is predicted or 0 otherwise) and the training is performed based on a well-described simulated dataset [3]. This dataset includes the time-varying network traffic for five 5G cellular areas and for different types of subscribers and UEs as bytes per time slot. The traffic data were reported for a period of 6 months and the total load of each cell was calculated as the added data-rate across its connected subscribers and devices, since we are not interested in the category-specific data but in the overall network traffic.

The forecasting ML task of the dynamic downlink data-rate is a regression task (the ML model outputs the upcoming value of the data-rate) and the training is performed based on two real datasets containing mobile traffic from multiple BSs². In

specific, mobile traffic is reported for three BSs located in a (sub)urban area and three BSs located close to a highway area in the city of Madrid [15]. The traffic load was measured for a varying time period depending on the BS (ranging up to 12 days) and different sampling rate (s or ms).

B. Training Results

For the anomaly detection task, we construct and train five DNNs to predict the total cell load anomaly, splitting each individual local dataset into training and testing sets (80/20 split). After extensive fine-tuning of the learning parameters, each DNN network consisted of one hidden layer with 200 units, while the learning rate was set to 0.001 and the lookback window to 96 samples. Similarly, for the forecasting task we construct and train three Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) networks for each dataset (urban/highway) consisting of 4 layers with 50 hidden units each, while utilizing a 80/20 split between the training/testing sets and a learning rate of 0.001. Furthermore, the selected loss functions (difference between the output of the ML model and the actual labels) were the Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE) loss for the DNN models (typically utilized in binary classification tasks with two classes) and the Mean Squared Error (MSE) for the LSTM models (typically utilized in regression tasks).

Fig. 4 shows the average MSE training loss with respect to the federated rounds across the three individual LSTM models and with a varying number of nodes that participate in the FL framework ($n = 2, 3$) using the urban dataset. The MSE loss shown for each FL round is also averaged across the $N = 10$ training local epochs that are performed locally by each node in each FL round, while the number of FedRA rounds is selected to be $M = 10$. Before the start of each federated round, the individual model parameters from the participating dApps are acknowledged to all other FedRA nodes and are fused by the use of the FedAvg algorithm into a global ML model. Fig. 4 also depicts the training loss of a typical Client-Server (C/S) FL approach, where it is assumed that a centralized entity (e.g., the near-RT RIC) is the server responsible for aggregating the ML model parameters from all clients, fusing them into a global model and distributing it to the participating nodes. Evidently, the achieved training losses coincide in the two FL schemes for this scenario, verifying the performance of FedRA-trained ML models in terms of prediction accuracy. Similar conclusions are derived for all three datasets, as summarized in Table I in terms of training and testing losses (the converged values after $M = 10$ FL rounds are tabulated).

C. Communication overhead considerations

Due to its fully decentralized architecture, FedRA incurs increased communication overhead among the nodes that participate in the framework when compared to more centralized approaches. To this end, we quantify the increased network traffic among the nodes in the FL framework due to the P2P model parameters exchange for the ML task and compare it to a typical client/server approach in Fig. 5 for the LSTM models that are trained on the three BS urban dataset. The

²<https://git2.networks.imdea.org/wng/madrid-lte-dataset>

Fig. 4. Average (across the N epochs of each FL round and across participating nodes) training loss in the FedRA framework compared to a typical client-server approach for the urban dataset.

P2P communication of the FedRA framework exhibits greater cumulative network traffic with respect to the client/server approach, which becomes increasingly evident with increasing number of participating peers. In this context, the total size of model updates that are exchanged with $n = 2$ peers in FedRA is 34.27 MB, whereas the cumulative network traffic among the dApps that are hosted in $n = 3$ FedRA nodes is 48.77 instead of 11.5 MB and 17.24 MB, respectively, which are exchanged in the client/server framework. For reference, the network traffic of a fully centralized approach without FL in the case of $n = 3$ nodes is 70.3 MB. In this case, all nodes send their time-series local datasets to the server that performs centrally the ML model training.

The total network traffic for the three datasets and the two FL schemes is also tabulated in Table I, along with the inference runtime of the respective models per sample, complying with the control loop 1 stringent latency constraints. Overall, the conclusions drawn from the results of both simulated and real datasets are similar in terms of achieved global model accuracy and network traffic, with FedRA showing increased traffic compared to the typical C/S scheme, while ensuring the benefits of the fully decentralized learning. It should be also noted that centralized, hierarchical and hybrid FL approaches reduce the network traffic (no need for all-to-all model transfers) compared to FedRA, but they typically require intermediate aggregation entities (e.g., MEC or RIC-level servers), which increases their dependency on semi-centralized control. Introducing such intermediate coordinators in O-RAN overloads the E2 interface, which is already responsible for real-time RAN control signaling.

The above analysis also denotes the key limitation of FedRA, illustrating the trade-off between the increased communication overhead and the resilience that the framework entails. As aforementioned, in FedRA no single point of failure exists and the FL training process continues even when individual nodes exit the framework due to limited availability as compared to typical client/server approaches. The robustness of the system, however, is inevitably tied with increased P2P

Fig. 5. Cumulative network traffic of FedRA and typical client/server approach for different number of participating peers in the FL frameworks for the urban dataset.

TABLE I
COMPARATIVE OUTCOMES OF FL SCHEMES ACROSS THREE DATASETS

Dataset	FL scheme	dApps (#)	Training Loss (<)	Testing Loss (<)	Total Network Traffic (MB)	Inference Runtime (ms)	
Synthetic [3]	FedRA	2	2e-3	0.05	12.54	0.86	
		3	2e-3	0.06	18.13	0.85	
		4	2e-3	0.06	19.55	0.85	
		5	2e-3	0.06	21.82	0.84	
	C/S	2	2e-3	0.06	3.14	0.86	
		3	2e-3	0.06	4.7	0.89	
		4	2e-3	0.06	6.27	0.92	
Urban [15]	FedRA	2	2e-5	3e-4	34.27	1.00	
		3	2e-5	2e-4	48.77	1.11	
	C/S	2	2e-5	3e-4	11.5	1.34	
		3	2e-5	3e-4	17.24	1.97	
	Highway [15]	FedRA	2	2e-5	2e-4	34.86	1.00
			3	2e-5	2e-4	50.51	1.11
C/S		2	2e-5	2e-4	11.5	1.34	
		3	2e-5	2e-4	17.24	1.97	

communications that can be reasonably tolerated in small-scale deployments (e.g., in cases of 3 or 4 different vendors that operate in the same O-RAN area), but significantly escalates with increasing number of peers.

D. Delay Components and Scalability Considerations

In this subsection, we discuss implementation details related to the dApp discovery and peer synchronization time in the FedRA framework, as well as provide considerations for the model exchange latency when the number of peers increases. Regarding the former, the initial peer discovery and synchronization is conducted by the P2P Communication Layer, where the peers publish their network state (e.g., Joined, Ready, Waiting, etc.). Simulation results demonstrate that the peer discovery and connection time exhibits an almost linear increase with respect to the number of peers. Regarding the model exchange between peers, FedRA supports a mixture of direct peer connections and k -gossip protocols to reduce network traffic. Since the major part of model handling and

transmission operations are conducted in parallel for each peer (e.g., the model serialization, the packet decapsulation, the transmission of the model parameters, etc.), the model exchange time does not dramatically escalate with an increasing number of peers. Implementation details of the above simulations and a hierarchical FL scheme can be found in the open-source FedRA code.

Concerning peer churn, node unavailability and, in general, failure of state synchronization between the peers, we have implemented a mechanism based on a maximum number of attempts, which is a tunable parameter of the FedRA framework. Hence, in case of receiver unavailability, the sending peer makes multiple attempts to transmit its model parameters after waiting a configurable inter-attempt time interval. In case that all attempts fail, the FL process is resumed, without the participation of the offline node. On the other hand, nodes joining the framework during the training can also be supported by FedRA. These nodes will receive the latest updated models from the online peers, they will compute the global FL model and continue the local epoch training process.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we present a fully decentralized FL framework in the O-RAN architecture, providing guidelines related to its realistic implementation. In this context, we outline the main concepts behind the O-RAN AI/ML deployment, as well as describing the FedRA workflow that can be used to collectively train ML models in different DUs/CUs, boosting the resilience and the security of the system and the generalization capabilities of the ML models. Finally, we demonstrate how different ML models can be collectively trained between multiple dApps hosted in DUs using real and simulated datasets from different RUs, comparing the performance results with a typical client/server FL approach, while also quantifying the communication overhead that the decentralized architecture incurs. Future extensions of FedRA will incorporate secure aggregation schemes to protect model confidentiality, Byzantine-robust aggregation rules (e.g., Krum, trimmed-mean, or median-based), and distributed confirmation mechanisms using tamper-evident ledgers to trace model-update provenance. These measures may collectively strengthen the trustworthiness of decentralized intelligence sharing across multi-vendor O-RAN deployments.

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